

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 105

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 105

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 105:1 Oh ^agive thanks to the LORD, ^bcall upon His name; ^cMake known His deeds among the peoples.</p> <p>² Sing to Him, ^asing praises to Him; ^{1b}Speak of all His ²wonders.</p> <p>³ ¹Glory in His holy name; Let the ^aheart of those who seek the LORD be glad.</p> <p>⁴ Seek the LORD and ^aHis strength; ^bSeek His face continually.</p> <p>⁵ Remember His ^{1a}wonders which He has done, His marvels and the ^bjudgments ²uttered by His mouth,</p> <p>⁶ O seed of ^aAbraham, His servant, O sons of ^bJacob, His ^cchosen ones!</p> <p>⁷ He is the LORD our God; His ^ajudgments are in all the earth.</p>	<p>Psa. 105:1 תוֹדוֹ לַיהוָה קְרָאוּ בְשֵׁמוֹ הוֹדִיעוּ בְּעַמִּים עֲלִילוֹתָיו : ² שִׁירוּ-לוֹ וּמְרוּ-לוֹ שִׁיחוּ בְּכָל-נִפְלְאוֹתָיו : ³ הִתְהַלְלוּ בְּשֵׁם קְדֹשׁוֹ יִשְׁמַח לֵב וּמִבְקֵשֵׁי יְהוָה : ⁴ וְדַרְשׁוּ יְהוָה וְעֹזוֹ בִּקְשׁוּ פָנָיו תָּמִיד : ⁵ זְכוּרוּ נִפְלְאוֹתָיו אֲשֶׁר-עָשָׂה לְמוֹפְתָיו וּמִשְׁפָּטֵי-פִיו : ⁶ זֶרַע אַבְרָהָם עֲבָדוֹ בְּנֵי יַעֲקֹב בְּחִירָיו : ⁷ הוּא יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ בְּכָל-הָאָרֶץ מִשְׁפָּטָיו : ⁸ זָכַר לְעוֹלָם בְּרִיתוֹ דָּבָר צִוְּהָ לְאַלְף דּוֹר : ⁹ אֲשֶׁר פָּרַת אֶת-אַבְרָהָם וּשְׁבוּעָתוֹ לְיִשְׁחָק : ¹⁰ וַיַּעֲמִידָהּ לְיַעֲקֹב לְחֹק לְיִשְׂרָאֵל בְּרִית עוֹלָם : ¹¹ לֵאמֹר לְךָ אֶתֵּן אֶת-אֶרֶץ-כְּנָעַן חֶבְל נַחֲלַתְכֶם : ¹² בְּהִיוֹתְהֶם מְתֵי מִסְפָּר כְּמַעַט וַיְגַרִּים בָּהֶם : ¹³ וַיִּתְּהַלְכוּ מִגּוֹי אֶל-גּוֹי מִמַּמְלָכָה אֶל-עַם אֲחֵר : ¹⁴ לֹא-הִנִּיחַ אֲדָם לְעַשְׂקֵם וַיִּזְכַּח עֲלֵיהֶם מַלְכִים : ¹⁵ אֶל-תִּגְעוּ בְּמִשְׁחֵי וַלְנַבִּיאֵי אֶל-תִּרְעוּ : ¹⁶ וַיִּקְרָא רָעַב עַל-הָאָרֶץ כָּל-מִטְהַ לֶחֶם שָׁבַר : ¹⁷ שָׁלַח לְפָנֵיהֶם אִישׁ לְעֹבֵד נִמְכָּר יוֹסֵף : ¹⁸ עָנּוּ בְּכַפָּל רַגְלָיו [רַגְלוֹ]</p>
<p>Psa. 105:8 He has ^aremembered His covenant forever, The word which He commanded to a ^bthousand generations, ⁹ <i>The ^acovenant</i> which He made with Abraham, And His ^boath to Isaac.</p> <p>¹⁰ Then He ^aconfirmed it to Jacob for a statute, To Israel as an everlasting covenant,</p> <p>¹¹ Saying, “^aTo you I will give the land of Canaan As the ^{1b}portion of your inheritance,”</p>	

12 When they were only a "few men in number,

Very few, and ^bstrangers in it.

13 And they wandered about from nation to nation,

From *one* kingdom to another people.

14 He ^apermitted no man to oppress them,

And He ^breproved kings for their sakes:

15 "Do not touch My anointed ones,
And do My prophets no harm."

Psa. 105:16 And He ^acalled for a famine upon the land;

He ^bbroke the whole staff of bread.

17 He ^asent a man before them,
Joseph, *who* was ^bsold as a slave.

18 They afflicted his ^afeet with fetters,
¹He himself was laid in irons;

19 Until the time that his ^aword came to pass,

The word of the LORD ^{1b}tested him.

20 The ^aking sent and released him,
The ruler of peoples, and set him free.

21 He ^amade him lord of his house
And ruler over all his possessions,

22 To ¹imprison his princes ^{2a}at will,
That he might teach his elders wisdom.

23 ^aIsrael also came into Egypt;
Thus Jacob ^bsojourned in the land of Ham.

24 And He ^acaused His people to be very fruitful,

And made them stronger than their adversaries.

בְּרִזְלָא בָּאָה נִפְשׁוֹ : 19 עַד-עֵת בָּא-

דְּבָרוֹ אִמְרַת יְהוָה צָרְפָתָהּ : 20

נִשְׁלַח מִלְךְ וַיִּתְּיָרְהוּ מִשָּׁל עַמִּים

וַיִּבְתְּתָהּ : 21 שָׁמוּ אֲדוֹן לְבֵיתוֹ

וּמִשָּׁל בְּכָל-קַנְיָנוֹ : 22 לְאַסֵּר שָׂרָיו

בְּנִפְשׁוֹ וּזְקַנָּיו יִחַסֵּם : 23 וַיָּבֵא

יִשְׂרָאֵל מִצְרַיִם וַיַּעֲקֹב גַּר בְּאֶרֶץ-

חָם : 24 וַיִּפְרֹ אֶת-עַמּוֹ מְאֹד

וַיַּעֲצֵמָהּ מִצְרַיִם : 25 הִפְךָ לָבָם

לְשֵׁנָא עַמּוֹ לְהִתְנַפֵּל בְּעַבְדָּיו : 26

שָׁלַח מֹשֶׁה עַבְדּוֹ אֶתְהֹן אֲשֶׁר

בְּחֶרֶב-בּוֹ : 27 שָׁמוּ-בָם דְּבָרַי אֶתְהֵיוּ

וּמִכְּפֹתַיִם בְּאֶרֶץ חָם : 28 שָׁלַח חֹשֶׁף

וַיִּחֲשֹׁף וְלֹא-אָמְרוּ אֶת-דְּבָרוֹ

[וְדָבְרוּ :] 29 הִפְךָ אֶת-מִימֵיהֶם לָדָם

וַיִּמָּת אֶת-דֹּגְתָם : 30 שָׂרְיָא אֲרָצִים

צִפְרֻדֵּי-עֵיִם בְּחֶדְרָי מִלְכֵיהֶם : 31

אָמַר וַיָּבֵא עֲרֹב כְּנִים בְּכָל-

גְּבוּלָם : 32 נָתַן גִּשְׁמֵיהֶם בְּרֶד אֵשׁ

לְהַבּוֹת בְּאֲרָצִים : 33 וַיִּיָּךְ גִּבּוֹנִים

וַתֵּאֲנַתֶּם וַיִּשְׁפֹּר עֵץ גְּבוּלָם : 34 אָמַר

וַיָּבֵא אֲרָבָה וַיִּלְקַח וַאֲיִן מִסִּפְרָא : 35

וַיֵּאֱכַל כָּל-עַשְׂבַּת בְּאֲרָצִים וַיֵּאֱכַל

כָּרִי אֲדָמָתָם : 36 וַיִּיָּךְ כָּל-בְּכוֹר

בְּאֲרָצִים רִאשִׁית לְכָל-אוֹנָם : 37

וַיִּזְצִיאוּם בְּכֶסֶף וְזָהָב וַאֲיִן בְּשִׁבְטָיו

כּוֹשֵׁל : 38 שָׁמַת מִצְרַיִם בְּצִאתָם

כִּי-נִפְלַח פַּחַדָּם עֲלֵיהֶם : 39 פָּרַשׁ

Psa. 105:25 He ^aturned their heart to hate His people,

To ^bdeal craftily with His servants.

²⁶ He ^asent Moses His servant,

And ^bAaron, whom He had chosen.

²⁷ They ^{1a}performed His wondrous acts among them,

And miracles in the land of Ham.

²⁸ He ^asent darkness and made *it* dark;

And they did not ^brebel against His words.

²⁹ He ^aturned their waters into blood And caused their fish to die.

³⁰ Their land swarmed with ^afrogs Even in the ^bchambers of their kings.

³¹ He spoke, and there came a ^aswarm of flies

And ^bgnats in all their territory.

³² He ¹gave them ^ahail for rain,

And flaming fire in their land.

³³ He ^astruck down their vines also and their fig trees,

And shattered the trees of their territory.

³⁴ He spoke, and ^alocusts came, And young locusts, even without number,

³⁵ And ate up all vegetation in their land, And ate up the fruit of their ground.

³⁶ He also ^astruck down all the firstborn in their land,

The ^bfirst fruits of all their vigor.

Psa. 105:37 Then He brought them out with ^asilver and gold,

עָנַן לְמַסְדָּךְ וְאֵשׁ לְהַאֲרִיר לַיְלָה : ⁴⁰
שָׁאֵל וַיָּבֵא שְׁלוֹ וְלֶחֶם שָׁמַיִם
יִשְׁבִּיעֵם : ⁴¹ פָּתַח צֹר וַיִּזְוּבוּ מַיִם
הִלְכוּ בַצִּיּוֹת נִהָר : ⁴² כִּי־זָכַר אֶת־
דְּבַר קִדְשׁוֹ אֶת־אַבְרָהָם עֶבְדּוֹ : ⁴³
וַיִּזְצֵא עַמּוֹ בְּשִׁשּׁוֹן בְּרָנְהָ אֶת־
בְּחִירָיו : ⁴⁴ וַיִּתֵּן לָהֶם אֲרָצוֹת גּוֹיִם
וַעֲמַל לְאֻמִּים יִירָשׁוּ : ⁴⁵ בַּעֲבוּר אֶל־
יִשְׁמְרוּ חֻקָּיו וְתוֹרָתוֹ יִנְצְרוּ הַלְלוּ־
יְהוָה :

And among His tribes there was not one who stumbled.

³⁸ Egypt was ^aglad when they departed,

For the ^bdread of them had fallen upon them.

³⁹ He spread a ^acloud for a ¹covering, And ^bfire to illumine by night.

⁴⁰ ¹They ^aasked, and He brought ^bquail,

And satisfied them with the ^{2a}bread of heaven.

⁴¹ He opened the ¹rock and ^awater flowed out;

²It ran in the dry places *like* a river.

⁴² For He ^aremembered His holy word

With Abraham His servant;

⁴³ And He brought forth His people with joy,

His chosen ones with a joyful ^ashout.

⁴⁴ He ^agave them also the lands of the ¹nations,

That they ^bmight take possession of *the fruit of* the peoples' labor,

⁴⁵ So that they might ^akeep His statutes

And observe His laws,

¹Praise ²the LORD!

References

Psalm 105:1

^a1 Chr 16:8-22, 34; Ps 106:1; Is 12:4

^bPs 99:6

^cPs 145:12

Psalm 105:2

¹Or *Meditate on*

²I.e. wonderful acts

^aPs 96:1; 98:5

^bPs 77:12; 119:27; 145:5

Psalm 105:3

¹Or *Boast*

^aPs 33:21

Psalm 105:4

^aPs 63:2

^bPs 27:8

Psalm 105:5

¹I.e. wonderful acts

²Lit *of His mouth*

^aPs 40:5; 77:11

^bPs 119:13

Psalm 105:6

^aPs 105:42

^bPs 135:4

^c1 Chr 16:13; Ps 106:5; 135:4

Psalm 105:7

^aIs 26:9

Psalm 105:8

^aPs 105:42; 106:45; Luke 1:72

^bDeut 7:9

Psalm 105:9

^aGen 12:7; 17:2, 8; 22:16-18; Gal 3:17

^bGen 26:3

Psalm 105:10

^aGen 28:13-15

Psalm 105:11

¹Lit *measuring line*

^aGen 13:15; 15:18

^bJosh 23:4; Ps 78:55

Psalm 105:12

^aGen 34:30; Deut 7:7

^bGen 23:4; Heb 11:9

Psalm 105:14

^aGen 20:7; 35:5

^bGen 12:17; 20:3, 7

Psalm 105:15

^aGen 26:11

Psalm 105:16

^aGen 41:54

^bLev 26:26; Is 3:1; Ezek 4:16

Psalm 105:17

^aGen 45:5

^bGen 37:28, 36; Acts 7:9

Psalm 105:18

¹Lit *His soul came into*

^aGen 39:20; 40:15

Psalm 105:19

¹Or *refined*

^aGen 40:20, 21

^bPs 66:10

Psalm 105:20

^aGen 41:14

Psalm 105:21

^aGen 41:40-44

Psalm 105:22

¹Lit *bind*

²Lit *at his*

^aGen 41:44

Psalm 105:23

^aGen 46:6; Acts 7:15

^bActs 13:17

Psalm 105:24

^aEx 1:7, 9

Psalm 105:25

^aEx 1:8; 4:21

^bEx 1:10; Acts 7:19

Psalm 105:26

^aEx 3:10; 4:12

^bEx 4:14; Num 16:5; 17:5-8

Psalm 105:27

¹Lit *set the words of His signs*

^aPs 78:43-51; 105:27-36

Psalm 105:28

^aEx 10:21, 22

^bPs 99:7

Psalm 105:29

^aEx 7:20, 21

Psalm 105:30

^aEx 8:6

^bEx 8:3

Psalm 105:31

^aEx 8:21

^bEx 8:16, 17

Psalm 105:32

¹Or *made their rain hail*

^aEx 9:23-25

Psalm 105:33

^aPs 78:47

Psalm 105:34

^aEx 10:12-15

Psalm 105:36

^aEx 12:29; 13:15; Ps 135:8; 136:10

^bGen 49:3

Psalm 105:37

^aEx 12:35, 36

Psalm 105:38

^aEx 12:33

^bEx 15:16

Psalm 105:39

¹Or *curtain*

^aEx 13:21; Neh 9:12; Ps 78:14; Is 4:5

^bEx 40:38

Psalm 105:40

¹Or *One*

²Or *food*

^aEx 16:12; Ps 78:18

^bEx 16:13; Num 11:31; Ps 78:27

^cEx 16:15; Neh 9:15; Ps 78:24; John 6:31

Psalm 105:41

¹Or *boulder*

²Lit *They went*

^aEx 17:6; Num 20:11; Ps 78:15; 114:8; Is 48:21; 1 Cor 10:4

Psalm 105:42

^aGen 15:13, 14; Ps 105:8

Psalm 105:43

^aEx 15:1; Ps 106:12

Psalm 105:44

¹Or *Gentiles*

^aJosh 11:16-23; 13:7; Ps 78:55

^bDeut 6:10, 11

Psalm 105:45

¹Or *Hallelujah!*

²Heb *YAH*

^aDeut 4:1, 40

Targum

Psa. 105:1 Sing praise in the presence of the LORD, call on his name; tell of his deeds among the Gentiles. ² Sing praise in his presence, make music in his presence; speak of all his wonders. ³ Sing praise in his holy name; may the heart of those who seek instruction from the presence of the LORD be glad. ⁴ Seek the teaching of the LORD, and his Torah; welcome his face continually. ⁵ Call to mind the wonders that he has done; his miracles, and the judgments of his mouth. ⁶ O seed of Abraham his servant, O sons of Jacob, his chosen ones – ⁷ He is the LORD our God; his judgments are extended over all the earth. ⁸ He remembered his covenant forever; he commanded a word for a thousand generations. ⁹ That which he made with Abraham, and his covenant with Isaac. ¹⁰ And he established it for Jacob as a decree, for Israel as a perpetual covenant. ¹¹ Saying, “To you I will give the land of Canaan as the lot of your inheritance.” ¹² When you were a people few in number, like little ones, and dwelling in it. ¹³ And they went from people to people, from one kingdom to [another people.] ¹⁴ He did not allow anyone to oppress them, and he rebuked kings on their account. ¹⁵ Do not come near my anointed ones, and do no harm to my prophets. ¹⁶ And he proclaimed a famine against the land; he broke every support of food. ¹⁷ He sent a wise man before them; Joseph was sold as a slave. ¹⁸ They afflicted his feet with chains; a collar of iron went on his soul. ¹⁹ Until the time when his word came true; the word of the LORD purified him. ²⁰ He sent a king and freed him; a ruler of peoples, and he set him free. ²¹ He made him master of his house, and ruler of all his property. ²² To bind his princes to, as it were, his soul; and he grew wiser than his elders. ²³ And Israel came to Egypt, and Jacob dwelt in the land of Ham. ²⁴ And he made his people very numerous, and made it stronger than its oppressors. ²⁵ Their heart was changed to hate his people, to plot evil things against his servants. ²⁶ He sent Moses his servant, Aaron, with whom he was pleased. ²⁷ They set among them the decrees of his signs, and wonders in the land of Ham. ²⁸ He sent darkness and darkened them, and they did not rebel against his word. ²⁹ He turned their water into blood, and killed all their fish. ³⁰ Their land crawled with frogs in the chambers of their kings. ³¹ He spoke, and brought swarms, vermin in all their territory. ³² He gave their rain as hail, blazing fire in their land. ³³ And he smote their vines and their figs, and smashed the trees of their territory. ³⁴ He spoke, and brought locusts, and grasshoppers without number. ³⁵ And they obliterated all the grass in their land, and consumed the fruits of their land. ³⁶ And he smote every firstborn in Egypt, the beginning of all their strength. ³⁷ And he brought them out with silver and with gold, and they did not quarrel with the Egyptians about the weight. ³⁸ The Egyptians rejoiced when they left, for fear of them had fallen upon them. ³⁹ He spread out the clouds like a curtain, and fire to give light at night. ⁴⁰ They asked for flesh and he brought quail; and he will satisfy them with the bread of heaven. ⁴¹ He opened the rock and water flowed; it went into the dry places like a river. ⁴² For he remembered his holy utterance with Abraham his servant. ⁴³ And he brought out his people in joy, his

chosen ones with praise. ⁴⁴ And he gave to them the lands of the Gentiles; and they will inherit the labor of the peoples. ⁴⁵ In order that they might keep his ordinances, and observe his Torah. Hallelujah!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm was composed on the day King David brought the Ark of the Covenant from its temporary location in the home of Oved Edon to the holy city of Jerusalem. There was a lavish ceremony that day for the LORD. The Psalmist emphasizes that the Jews who escorted the Ark were the children of Abraham. Abraham's greatest accomplishment was traveling from place to place, teaching the Name of the One God, the LORD. The Ark represents the name of the LORD. When David carried the Ark from place to place, he resembled his illustrious forebear Abraham.

Verse three

Seeking your glory in the name of the LORD is done by persons who want to follow the ways of the Torah

Seek your glory in His Holy Name, so that the heart of those that seek God may rejoice.

Notes on this Psalm

It seems today that young people generally do not care about history. That is sad because it is through the historical record that a person finds the works of the LORD. Judaism is a religion dedicated to the LORD because of the nation's history. This Psalm highlights Israel's national history. Throughout her history, one can find the LORD at work. Secular Jews have also forgotten this. The children of Abraham became the Chosen people of the LORD because of the events in Egypt and Mount Sinai. The Passover cements the future generations of Jews to the LORD. A Midrash

says that all Jewish souls came into the valley at Mount Sinai when the LORD presented the Ten Commandments and the Torah. The LORD asked whether the souls would abide by the Torah. In exchange, the LORD said he would always be with the people. These people were the only Earth nation willing to accept the LORD's protection in exchange for the Torah.

History proves that when the nation followed the Torah, the LORD protected them and gave them prosperity. When the country violated the Torah, the LORD's anger was the removal of His protection. As long as a Jew tries to live by the Torah, the LORD will always be with the person. This understanding has been expressed in prior Psalms. For the Jew, the dedication to the LORD is through history first and personal experiences second. It is the greatest honor to say that one belongs to the Chosen People.

Other nations are invited to partake in the LORD's grace by accepting the Torah. Unfortunately, in most cases, the Goyim have decided to punish the nation of Israel by persecuting the Children of Abraham, whether they happen to be living. Human history would be less bloody if the Goyim accepted the LORD.

The Christian Messiah Yeshua brought this message to the Jews under Roman persecution. He told them to repent! That meant going back to living by the Torah. Many did so, and many followed Yeshua to learn from him how to live by the Torah in their world. Today one can find ways to follow the LORD's Torah through the words and acts of Yeshua of Nazareth. Sadly, Yeshua churches have so many antisemitic members. They have distorted Yeshua of Nazareth's teaching into a form

that allowed the Christian Church to take over most of Europe for centuries. The backlash from the Church's control of Europe is still being seen today. Yeshua did not want to create a new religion. He wanted his Jewish brothers and sisters to return to Torah living. The second part of his mission was to bring the Gentiles into the Kingdom of Heaven, which meant they would also follow the Torah.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

